

Supplementary Information File 4: Selection Based on the Learning Cues

Rationale

The original selection of meter-related and meter-unrelated frequencies was determined from both the stimulus spectrum and plausible beat periodicities to which participants could clap to (see ‘Sound Analysis’ section in the Methods of the main manuscript). However, the 2.5 Hz had to be excluded, as it represented a harmonic common to both metrical interpretations. Consequently, several participants ($k = 3$) who steadily clapped at 400 ms (i.e., the three-beat metrical interpretation) were attributed a relatively low three-beat meter-related z score due to the spectral energy being concentrated around the 2.5 Hz bin. To control for this possible methodological confound, an alternative selection of meter-related frequencies based on the learning cues during the body-movement session was also considered (i.e., cue at 800 ms and 600 ms for the three-beat metre and the four-beat metre condition, respectively). In the three-beat condition, this selection identifies 1.25 Hz (i.e., 1/0.8 s) and its harmonics as meter-related, while 1.66 Hz (i.e., 1/0.6 s) and its harmonic are considered meter-unrelated; the converse applies for the four-beat condition.

EEG Data

The RM ANOVA showed no significant main effect of session $F(1, 38) = 0.917, p = .344, \eta^2_p = .024$, or movement condition, $F(1, 38) = 0.69, p = .411, \eta^2_p = .018$ (see Figure S4.1). The Session \times Movement Condition interaction was also nonsignificant, $F(1, 38) = .253, p = .618, \eta^2_p < .01$.

Figure S4.1

Neural Responses during the Pre- and Post-Movement Session

Note. Panel A: Magnitude spectra of neural responses averaged across participants for both sessions and conditions. Three-beat– and 4-beat related frequencies are highlighted in red and blue, respectively, and metre-unrelated frequencies are shown in black. Frequency-domain responses were merged across conditions in the pre-movement session, as experimental conditions only differed during the body-movement session. Panel B: Normalised z scores (i.e., range of -1 to +1) at metre-related frequencies across sessions and conditions. Individual values are shown as scatter points, with medians and quartiles represented by boxplots.

Behavioural Data (Pre- and Post-Movement Sessions)

The RM ANOVA showed no significant main effect of session $F(1, 38) = 5.41, p = .026, \eta^2_p = .12$, but there was a main effect of movement condition, $F(1, 38) = 7.17, p = .011, \eta^2_p = .16$, with larger $\bar{z}_{\text{clapping}}$ in the four-beat condition ($M = 1.00, SD = 0.96$) when compared to the three-beat condition ($M = 0.38, SD = 0.77, d = 0.71 > \text{SESOI}$; see Figure S4.2). The Session \times Movement Condition interaction was nonsignificant, $F(1, 38) = 1.14, p = .291, \eta^2_p = .03$. Overall, the additional results for neural responses are identical to those obtained with the

original selection of frequencies of interest. For behavioural responses, the main effect of session is no longer significant, with a p value now slightly above the α set at .020, but a new main effect of condition in line with the cultural hypothesis emerges.

Figure S4.2

Behavioural Responses (Selection of Metre-Related Frequencies Based on Learning Cues).

Note. Panel A: Magnitude spectra of clapping responses averaged across participants for both sessions and conditions. Three-beat and 4-beat metre-related frequencies are highlighted in red and blue, respectively, and meter-unrelated frequencies are highlighted in black. Note that IRIs and the magnitude spectra from all participants were merged across conditions in the pre-movement session as experimental conditions only differed in the body-movement session. Panel B: Normalised z scores (i.e., range of -1 to +1) at metre-related frequencies across sessions and conditions. Sessions are pooled together in order to show the significant effect of condition, in line with the culturally conventional metrical interpretation associated with this rhythm. Individual values are shown as scatter points, with medians and quartiles represented by boxplots. $**p < .02$.